

ON CERTAIN SALTS OF ALKALOIDS.

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A few salts of quinine, emetine and ephedrine have been described.

Owing to the toxicity and various other untoward reactions, the usefulness of salts of alkaloids in therapeutics is restricted. Thus, the injection of emetine hydrochloride is always painful and the drug has a depressant action on the heart muscle and produces cardiac irregularities. Similarly the ephedrine salts exert a considerable depressant action on the cardiac muscle and often (*cf.* Chin and Schmidt, *Medicine*, 1930, 9, 1) produce toxic symptoms such as nervous excitement and palpitation. Certain esters of quinine are tasteless but there is loss of efficiency due to decreased quinine content. Amongst the non-bitter quinine salts quinine tannate may be mentioned, but it contains only 33 per cent quinine and is slowly decomposed in the intestine. A systematic investigation is being carried out in this laboratory to find suitable salts of alkaloids for therapeutic use (*cf.* Basu, *Science and Culture*, 1937, 2, 363, 466). But as some of these salts have been prepared and published elsewhere, it has been deemed necessary to publish the results so far obtained.

EXPERIMENTAL

Emetine-d-camphor-β-sulphonate.—Emetine base in chloroform was prepared by decomposing emetine hydrochloride ($C_{22}H_{32}O_4N_2 \cdot 2HCl, 7H_2O$) (35 g.) in minimum quantity of double distilled water with dilute caustic soda solution till the mixture was alkaline and then extracting with chloroform. The chloroform extract was washed with cold water and to it *d*-camphor-β-sulphonic acid (23.5 g.) was added and well shaken. After a few minutes the solvent was distilled at 40-50° under reduced pressure and the residual mass was cooled and triturated with petroleum ether. A crystalline solid separated out. This was collected and on crystallisation from a mixture of alcohol and dry ether was obtained in clusters of fine needles, m. p. 203-4° (slow heating). (Found: N, 3.01. $C_{29}H_{40}O_4N_2 \cdot 2C_{10}H_{16}O_4S$ requires N, 2.97 per cent).

The salt is very soluble in water and a 9.04% solution, *i.e.* a solution containing the equivalent of 1 grain of emetine base in 1 c.c. (the usual therapeutic dose), has p_H ca 4.9. This solution can be sterilised by tyndallisation or by filtration. It possesses the specific action of emetine in amoebic dysentery and is much less toxic and better tolerated than emetine hydrochloride.

Ephedrine Camphorsulphonate.—A concentrated aqueous solution of ephedrine hydrochloride was made strongly alkaline with sodium hydroxide (50% solution) and the base was extracted with chloroform. The chloroform solution after being dried with anhydrous sodium sulphate, was treated with molecular proportion of camphorsulphonic acid at room temperature (25°). The white residue, obtained on concentration on the steam-bath at reduced pressure, was crystallised from boiling ethyl acetate in fine silky needles, m. p. 173-74° (with previous shrinkage). (Found: N, 3.98; $C_{16}H_{13}ON_3$, $C_{10}H_{16}O_2S$ requires N, 3.53 per cent). The amount of the ephedrine base present in the salt as estimated by the method of Giffen (*Pharm Weekblad*, 1936, 73, 526) (slightly modified) was 41.16 per cent. Theory requires 41.56 per cent.

This ephedrine salt is readily soluble in water, alcohol and chloroform but insoluble in ether, ligroin or petrol ether. A 6% percent solution of the salt had pH ca. 5.4. Its physiological properties are being determined in detail; it may be stated that in a case of allergic asthma it gave better relief by a fall in the respiratory rate.

(WITH M. ROY)

Quinine Camphorsulphonate.—The solid that separated when a solution of quinine (1 part) in chloroform was added to a solution of camphorsulphonic acid (2 parts) in the same solvent on slight warming was collected, washed with boiling ethyl acetate and finally crystallised from alcohol diluted with ether, m. p. 218-19°. (Found: N, 3.41; $C_{20}H_{24}O_2N_2$, $2C_{10}H_{16}O_2S$ requires N, 3.55 per cent). It is readily soluble in water but bitter in taste, and its aqueous solution is acid to litmus (cf. Bazzola, *La Sci. del Farm.*, 1937, 6, 279).

Quinine Mandelate.—An alcoholic solution of mandelic acid (3 g.) and quinine base (3.2 g.) was heated till the solution was neutral. It was cooled and diluted with ether when the salt separated. By dissolution in alcohol and precipitation with ether it was obtained as a flocculent mass, m. p. 189-90°. (Found: N, 6.03. $C_{20}H_{24}O_2N_2$, $C_8H_8O_2$ requires N, 5.88 per cent). It is better and is very sparingly soluble in water.

Quinine-2-oxynaphthoate.—The quinine base and 2-oxynaphthoic acid were dissolved in chloroform in molecular proportions and heated under reflux on a steam-bath. After most of the chloroform was distilled off, the salt was precipitated with the addition of petroleum ether, and

repeatedly washed with ether, and finally crystallised from a mixture of chloroform and ether, m.p. 149-50°. It gave low nitrogen value on analysis. The quinine base in the salt as determined by the extraction method was found to be 63.19, whereas theory requires the salt ($C_{20}H_{24}O_2N_2$, $C_{11}H_8O_6$) to contain 63.28%. It is slightly bitter in taste, difficultly soluble in alcohol and insoluble in water.

Quinine-1:1'-methylene-2:2'-dinaphthyl-3:3'-dicarboxylate.—When 1:1'-methylene-2:2'-dinaphthyl-3:3'-dicarboxylic acid (1 part) dissolved in the requisite quantity of sodium carbonate solution was gradually added to a solution of quinine dihydrochloride (molecular proportion), a curdy precipitate was obtained. After standing it was filtered, washed with water and crystallised from absolute alcohol in microscopic canary yellow needles, m.p. 199-200°. (Found: N, 3.61. $C_{20}H_{24}O_2N_2$, $C_{23}H_{16}O_6$ requires N, 3.93 per cent). It is slightly bitter, almost insoluble in water but readily dissolves in chloroform.

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